

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF MXENE/GRAPHENE/POLYMER MATRIX NANOCOMPOSITES

K. Zukiene^{1*}, G. Monastyreckis¹, S. Kilikevicius¹, M. Omastová², A. Aniskevich³
and D. Zeleniakiene¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kaunas University of Technology, Kaunas, Lithuania,

² Polymer Institute, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia,

³ Institute for Mechanics of Materials, University of Latvia, Ryga, Latvia

* Corresponding author (kristina.zukiene@ktu.lt)

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1 Introduction

The outstanding effect of nano reinforcement on mechanical properties of nanocomposites is related to the high specific surface area of nanofiller, strong filler-matrix interfacial adhesion as well as the properties of filler and polymer matrix. In recent years, two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials have received significant attention from academia and industries, with graphene as the most popular material due to its excellent electric, mechanical, and other properties [1,2]. The properties of graphene and polymer matrix interfaces are known. Graphene has hydrophobic surface resulting in agglomeration, poor compatibility, weak interfaces and insufficient mechanical reinforcement effect [2]. To improve the surface properties of graphene modification of surface properties is necessary.

Recently, a new family of 2D nanomaterials MXene was discovered [3]. MXenes has uncommon combination of metallic conductivity and hydrophilicity that is the key to the promise these materials have engendered [1,4]. Hydrophilicity is an important feature of MXenes that could determine the strong interface interaction between MXene nanosheet and matrix, and dispersibility in polymers. In order to utilize the advantages of MXene in MXene/graphene/polymer matrix nanocomposites, a comprehensive understanding of MXene surface properties is crucial, therefore the aim of this study was to determine the interfacial adhesion and compatibility at the MXene -matrix interface and the overall composite performance.

2 Materials and Methods

Biresin® CR122 epoxy resin and hardener Biresin® CH122-5 were used for investigations (Young's modulus of 2.8 GPa; tensile strength of 80 MPa; elongation at break of 5.6 %).

On the basis of the literature data, the following mechanical properties of graphene and MXene were used for investigations: MXene: Young's modulus of 0.33 TPa [5]; tensile strength of 20 MPa [6]; elongation at break of 4.5 % [6]. Graphene: Young's modulus of 1 TPa; tensile strength of 130 MPa; elongation at break of 20 % [7].

For the better understanding of the interaction effects between MXene, graphene and the polymer matrix on the mechanical properties of nanocomposites, the inverse finite element (FE) modelling of microstructure was also used [6]. Different 2D models were analysed under tension conditions. The example of periodic unit cell model of nanocomposite with 1 % of graphene and 2.5 % of Ti_3C_2 volume fraction is shown in Fig. 1.

For the surface energy estimation, the MXene was assembled into a thin film by MILD method (LiF + HCl), vacuum filtered and vacuum dried. The water and diiodomethane contact angles were measured immediately after deposition of the liquid drop on the surface. At least five drops were examined and the results averaged for each test liquid.

3 Results and discussion

A relatively rough external surface of the micron-sized $Ti_3C_2T_x$ particles promote the interfacial

interaction among MXene and polymer matrix due to mechanical interlocking.

It was found that the interface tension between MXene and polymer matrix mostly depends on the polarity of matrix used.

FE analysis confirmed the MXene/polymer and graphene/polymer interfaces have a significant influence on the mechanical properties of nanocomposite. This effect could be related with the interaction between the nanoparticle with rough and very high surface area and polymer matrix, leading to the formation of a polymer layer with modified, perturbed chain structure.

Conclusions

The influence of the surface properties of the MXene on the interfacial adhesion at filler - matrix interface of MXene/graphene/polymer matrix nanocomposite was estimated. The results of finite element modelling display good agreement with experimental data.

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Fig.1 Periodic unit cell model of nanocomposite with 1 % of graphene and 2.5 % of Ti_3C_2 volume fraction